

CUSTOMER PERCEPTION POST; THE PANDEMIC TOWARDS THE PURCHASE OF FURNITURE AND INTERIOR PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *The purpose of this study; is to understand what changes have happened to post the pandemic; in the field of furniture; and interiors. There; has been a change; in terms of working and living conditions. There were many changes in the overall economy of our country. People experienced a mass exodus of labor from various streams of the manufacturing sector. The economy has been experiencing- changes; in terms of the prices of commodities and raw materials. Furniture manufacturing engages large-scale transportation and showroom rentals. The product needs to be spread over a large area as it is a high volume and high-value item. This research is to understand changes that have happed in various spears of customers' life through a study of their perception; in terms of both furniture and interior*

Design/ Methodology/ Approach: *The methodology followed was by engaging a questionnaire that covers various buying aspects of people in terms- of furniture and interiors for their homes and offices. A questionnaire; to probe so that it encompasses questions that would give us an idea- in terms of events, functions, and ceremonies that were either postponed, delayed or canceled; due to various reasons.*

The death of a family member, loss of a job, and changes in the income levels of a buyer have resulted in various changes in buying behavior. This research is to establish those factors of production that could be a win-win situation for both- the customers, retailers, and furniture manufacturers.

Originality: *This research was required to understand- what needs to be; done; to prevent losses just in case; there is the repetition of another pandemic shortly. Studied first time by the researcher to understand what changes could be adopted to keep the supply chain intact even if there is an eventuality of big-scale economic loss. An attempt in original to understand a 360-degree view to prevent the mass exodus of the labor force, better logistics and planning of transportation to different destinations*

Paper type: *Scholarly research based on the primary data collection*

Keywords: Customer perception, buying behavior, exodus of labor force, Creativity and new product development, Logistics and transportations, negotiation with suppliers, SWOT

analysis, ABDC analysis

INTRODUCTION:

The nature of business changed completely post the pandemic in the field of Furniture and Interiors. There has been delays in placing orders by customers. Customers in general would like to safe guard their savings and preserve liquidity in the near future. Hence their perception towards purchase of high value items is a bit delayed phenomena.

Furniture and Interiors play a major role in terms of expansion and house development. Interiors are sometimes a necessity. The retail business is an area which has competition from the e-commerce sites; customers still feel to have the face to face discussion when it comes to furniture[1]. The work life balance and home life balance got disturbed due to the changes in the working place. Many organizations have moved to the model of work from home and this facilitated people to move on from phase of life to another [2]. Cross- company, cross border, cross functional disruptions have happened in the post pandemic era, resulting in degrading of bilateral relationships between competing nations like china and India; hence raw materials that go in to furniture manufacturing has coming from the cross border have seen raise in price to a large extent[3]. Employee engagement was a challenge as movement of employees, artisans, skilled workers became a challenge. In general while buying furniture it is a normal practice to take quotation before buying and these quotation went completely out of control as prices kept changing constantly during and post pandemic [4]. Life and death are two sides of a coin. What happens when death governs life, what happens when fear governs life; life at stake is the question; how many of us are ready to think of a home appliance or be it a furniture when death mongers on top of our head, we tend to protect life first and the rest second [5]. The goal of life and aim of life is different for each of us and it indicates what is feasible and what is not; when women strive for their family to succeed, women entrepreneurs are an example in terms of resilience to survive make their art to grow, make their nature to go head on in over coming challenges in spite of the pandemic, be it in schools and academic institutions [6]. This study is all about understanding each one's story of bouncing back and looking at life which in a different way. Each one's story is different. Employees have a different set of stories and when they belong to different sectors their perception and their feelings towards challenges and money are different. Employees have a fixed kind of income unless they do not have other sources of income. The post pandemic created a mindset that is that of protecting, preventing and less experimenting in life.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

The study shows that post pandemic things have developed in certain areas as well gone down in certain areas of business operations. The work environments have to be redesigned for suiting the changes post pandemic [7]. Urban design is essential for better prevention of any kind of pandemic, both indoor designs and city designs need to be upgraded accordingly[8]. The income of people got affected and people have opted to various methods of generating income to sustain their families and few of them are still continuing the same[9]. Agriculture also affected as the labour movement affected this sector too and the impact happened due to the transportation of

agricultural products [10]. Though the minimum guarantee incomes were planned by the big governments around the world India too had such income guarantees that helped people to mitigate their income challenges[11]. Post the pandemic the acceleration of the retail supply chain got ramped up but it got delayed over due to many vehicles that were abandoned as owners could not repay loans and many other issues popped up[12]. Consumer behavior toward e-commerce globally changed the way they were buying food or furniture and this accelerated as things became normal[13]. Post the pandemic building the omnichannel is the key for many companies and they started building up the franchises model as well as the new retail model[14]. Consumer started comparing the pricing and the models both on line as well as off line. There has been a change in the consumer behavior over a period of time[15]. The payments and salaries of people changed and they felt the need for novel payments like the credit facility or the debit card enhanced facility or online payments etc through the payments banks[16]. Countries like Turkey experienced changes though they are very strong in the exports of Furniture, they too came up with novel ideas to maintain same levels of exports[17]. Indonesia is one country in the south east asian countries which experienced a drastic drop in the furniture sales. They too came up with innovative payments mode[18]. Age is a matter of impact when it comes to buying and pensioners too buy as their requirements keep changing[19]. Consumer behavior changed drastically across nation for the greater good and people adopted new ways of sustaining the challenges[20].

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

The objective of the study is to understand few things and they are as follows; is there a change in the buying behavior of the employed class, is there is change in the products that they select, is there a change in the way they buy or is there a change in the way they delay their purchases. These are few questions which when structured in to a questionnaire gives us an idea of how people buy or postpone post pandemic.

RESEARCH AGENDA:

The research agenda is to understand and know the objectives that have been set for understanding the market especially the salaried class. The salaried class have a mind set of security and liability. The research is to understand whether their income has gone up or has gone down. This also fulfils the agenda to understand overall aspects of the Indian economy, from a small city like Mangalore a micro economic activity city when compared to the nation at large.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY: a questionnaire is designed and administered to a group of employees in different organizations. These organizations are Educational institutions, Manufacturing sector, Hospital sector, Government both state and central government employees.

SAMPLE SIZE: The Sample size taken is 200 employees out of which 50 of each sector; was selected. An average family income of Rs.25000/- and above was considered for the study

OBSERVATIONS: It is observed that most people have postponed their purchases as events

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in their life have postponed and have affected their overall confidence levels. These confidence levels have also created a subtle thought in minds that future ahead may be complicated and may not be as smooth or as clear as it was pre pandemic. These are a subtle observations observed by the researcher during the administration of the questionnaire. Indeed the employees category feels that people have fewer options as their salary or family income has not increased to a large extent. In general it has stayed the same for a long period of time.

Table: 1 Data analysis

Sl no.	Frequency		Percentage	Employee/ Respondent category
1	Gender		Male-65%	Male-130
			Female- 35%	Female-70
2	Age	28 to 70 years	28 to 45- 45%	Salaried
			46 to 60-44%	Salaried
			60 to 70-1%	Pensioner
3	Occupation	Employees	25%	Education sector-50 employees
			25%	Hospital Sector 50 employees
			25%	Manufacturing sector 50 employees
			25%	Government sector 50 employees
4	Income	25000 and above	All above 25000	All above 25000
5	Furniture purchased	Post Pandemic	80%	160 purchased based on the need only
6	Delay in delivery of furniture	Experienced by	92%	184 experienced delay in delivery
7	Post pandemic price	Experienced	96%	194 people experienced rise in

	increase	by		prices
8	Family programs postponed	Experienced by	45%	90 people experienced postponement of their family functions
9	Recovery of transportation and logistics of furniture industry	Experienced by	54%	108 people feel that transportation is not recovered
10	Payment through cards	Done by	85% Debit and credit cards	170 people pay through debit or credit cards
11	Visit to furniture store	Done by	64%	128 people visited the showroom
12	Post pandemic Income remains same	Experienced by	96%	194 people salary remained the same

Source: Compiled by the Researcher

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The customer visit to showroom has changed a bit. They would do showroaming and buy online as well as do webrooming and buy in a store. The purchase aspect of the customer to a large extent has changed to immediate decisions.

1. Most of the respondents would not order and wait for a long time; they feel the fear of any kind of slowdown or lockdown (around 80%)
2. Many customers would buy instantly if the product is on display (94%)
3. Many of the customers feel that payment via various modes would be risky hence they would opt for debit or credit cards. Most of them would not opt for an EMI mode
4. Many customers had experienced postponement of their family programs due to the pandemic and have changed the dates accordingly.
5. Indeed few customers want products at the same price as their salaries or family income has not changed drastically (96%) feel that their family incomes remained the same in spite of inflation.

FINDING: The customer purchase post pandemic has changed drastically as people visit only when they feel they need a product badly. They have either postponed their decisions or have gone for an alternative. People have choices and have started searching online for furniture and home products. Home products have a long lasting effect on their family members hence they would always look for warranty and after sales service in the products that they buy.

SWOC ANALYSIS: this is an analysis which makes things easier in terms of how customers feel and decide their purchases

Strength:the overall strength of a retail outlet is to understand that the strength of the location and the choice that customers have in visiting a showroom. Indeed this gives them confidence and agility to decide the colour, shape and size of the furniture. It also gives them the real time idea in terms of will the furniture fit in the space that they have at home

Weakness: Customers look for the changes and this can divert them to other shops. Variety seekers look for new products rather than durability and warranty. This can change the buying decision and the purchase behavior of the customers

Opportunity: There is ample opportunity post the pandemic; work from home has created a new product section all together in-terms of work stations for work from home changes

Challenges: The challenges that customer experience are the price rise and the changes that happened due to the exodus of the labour force and the subsequent delay in the delivery of the products.

SUGGESTIONS: Customers need products that are easy to carry, easy to install and easy to buy. They feel to save their money for the future emergency requirements. Hence companies need to make products that are less in cost and easy to install.

1. New products need to be developed using better designs with lighter material
2. New designs to be created using good designing softwares which can help the showfloor supervisor to understand and quick to produce
3. Make people know about these products using digital marketing and faster spread through social media
4. Conventional media costs a lot and hence the teams to be trained to look for alternative communications to spread the new design to a large number of customer
5. Develop sharing of information via various magazines which can help in locating new machine manufacturers
6. Come out with better skill training for faster and smoother delivery of products
7. Tie up with exclusive transportation companies to ensure there is on time delivery of products
8. Communicate these aspects of the research to all the employees of the organization

SCOPE FOR FUTURE RESEARCH:

Whenever such a situation come it means that in general people get in to a shell and hence they need to be assured that the cost is in line with their budget and it is better that they can understand by knowing the input cost. The future research can be done in the following areas:

1. How to bring down the cost
2. How to make economies of scale
3. How to build a strong learning team in the field of furniture

4. When to launch a new product as per the seasons
5. Green furniture to be considered and research to be done to know if people feel for green furniture

CONCLUSION:

We need to find out and study about new materials like green products that can be used in the making of furniture. This should bring down the costs as most of the employees income has not increased over this period of time. The idea is to understand what works and what does not work. Hence customers should have choice to buy from a plethora of products. This is possible when we use tabs or computers to show them the new designs and exclusive products. Exclusive products and new products lead to customization. Customization leads to better pricing and better pricing would lead to better margins and higher bonus to employees.

Research needs to be done in these lines for enhancing the income of employees to a large extent. This is all possible if new markets, exports can be undertaken.

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Appendix:

Questionnaire

Name:	E-mail id
Mobile No:	Currently working for:
Address:	Age: Gender:

1. Did you order for any furniture pre pandemic or during the pandemic or post pandemic
Yes No (Kindly tick-Pre-pandemic, pandemic, Post pandemic)
2. Was there a delay in the delivery of the furniture that you ordered?
Yes No
3. If there was delay; was it in the acceptable time frame?
Yes No
4. Do you feel there is a rise in the price post pandemic? What's your perception?
Yes No
5. Were anyone of your programs postponed due to the pandemic like: Housewarming, marriage in the family, child naming ceremony, shop inauguration and any other important programs?
Yes No
6. Do you feel that transport and logistics of furniture delivery and transportation recovered post pandemic?

Yes No

7. Based on your need and choice; do you place an order for furniture or buy immediately on seeing the furniture in the store
 - a. I/ we Place an order and wait
 - b. I/ we Buy instantly and do not wait
 - c. I/ we Don't know about the future
 - d. I/we Will not spend money
 - e. I/ we Will buy only when needed
8. Post the pandemic what is your buying process
 - a. All cash
 - b. Pay through credit cards
 - c. Take loan from friends
 - d. Consumer finance like Bajaj finance
 - e. Post pandemic I buy through Installments if the store permits
9. Post pandemic I visit the furniture retail store
 - a. Only when I feel I need
 - b. I/ we do window shopping
 - c. I/ we Look for exchange offers
 - d. I/ we Look for consumer offers
 - e. I/ we Look for new designs if any
10. Post pandemic my income has
 - a. I/ My family income has Increased
 - b. Same
 - c. Gone down
 - d. Retired
 - e. Lost my Job/closed by business